

Taxes and Unemployment in the Asean Countries

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ABSTRACT: This study has inspired us to understand the relationship between taxes and unemployment in ASEAN countries. Taxes are one of the sources of government development funding, including human development. The purpose of this study is to find out how much ASEAN four governments are taxed for inaction. The four ASEAN governments are used as examples. The methods used in this study were information verified using the eViews app, 12. The results showed that simultaneously the variables Foreign Domestic Investment, Exchange Rate have a positive and significant influence on tax revenue. Partially, Foreign Domestic Investment variables and exchange rates have a positive and significant influence, while exchange rate variables have a negative and insignificant influence on tax revenue. Furthermore, the variable of tax revenue has a positive and significant influence on unemployment. For this reason, governments in ASEAN countries need efforts so that tax revenues can increase so as to reduce unemployment in their respective countries.

KEYWORD: Foreign direct investment, import, exchange rate, taxes, unemployment

INTRODUCTION

It is important for the government to reform to meet the needs of the people as it has the resources to take advantage of the growing economy in the region. Accordingly, state expenditure in the form of taxes and not taxes and currency systems is influenced by the development budget. There are a number of factors that can motivate taxes such as direct spending from abroad, currency, and currency. High taxes allocate money for the development of the country. While our budget is much larger, the government can decide how much revenue should be imposed on a tax.

Tax

JM Keynes the role of the state in financial markets is crucial to stimulating the economy. To influence the country's revenues and revenues in the budget, the government needs to change public spending and taxes (Stubborn Nas, 2019, p. 1). This fiscal policy allows people to spend more and reduce government taxes, boost the global economy and slow economic growth.

Sumitro (2013, p. 1) People pay taxes in a museum based on rules that can be obtained without direct consideration. Correct research is that the impact of corporate taxes on unemployment "shows that tax increases lead to unemployment. (Chapters Zirgulis and Sar, 2017). In addition, a study titled "The Impact of Regional Taxes and Deposits on Unemployment Increases and High Costs" confirms that our local tax rate affects unemployment (Indra, 2016). Further studies such as "income tax on supplements" (Sun Ngoc, 2023).

Foreign Domestic Investment

Use of different countries a field that is used abroad or can travel nationwide for the benefit of the capital; (Jingan, 2018). *Use of different countries* 25, 2007 Law No. *Use of different countries* Financial services for businesses in the state of Indonesia, managed by foreign aid providers. Knowing this, Israel announced in 2016 that the country's capital is a foreign payment tool that is not part of Indonesia's wealth, and the government agreed to use it to pay Indonesia's corporate funds.

This study "motivates a person *Use of different countries* in larger countries in the form of tax revenues" shows the positive benefits of spending tax revenues correctly (God's sign) and al., 2019). "The impact of economic development, *Use of different countries* Sa'd Govern The tax laws of ASEAN member states confirm that foreign direct investments are indeed taxed at some point, but foreign direct investments do not affect tax revenues (In History, 2020). Read the article "Inspirational *Use of different countries* and the distribution of tax revenue in cities that support the ASEAN system to ensure that foreign currency has a positive impact on tax revenues. (A, A, etc., 2023).

Import

The process of purchasing a product or service from one place to another (Jordan, 2018, page 2) . Tax assistance must be sent to the country. As in the case of Ali Puritan Indian (2015.10), entry is a process that consists of sending goods to the order of the territory where individuals and legal entities travel and cross the state border, being forced to fulfill tax obligations such as paying nobility tax and intelligence tax. A similar study titled "Outcome of Change and Assignment Acceptance Entry Book" confirms that exchange fees and books have a significant impact at the same time.(Your quest, Revin & Edison, 2023). A study titled "Results of tax deposits: ĩma in Indonesia" suggests that currency growth will affect tax returns. (from Takahashi, 2012).

Exchange Rate

The exchange rate or exchange rate is the amount you must pay at home to receive foreign currency. The number of changes in a single home can be seen using utilities or human services (Gil 2, 2023). in terms of research and research." *The change in the tax system in Kenya is commensurate with the cost of the change, which affects tax revenues in Kenya.*(Ruto, 2020). Other research."*The impact of tax changes Sub-Saharan in Africa and can fix the exchange rate directly at the tax rate in sub-Saharan Africa;* (Isaac, Kamara & Peter, 2021) . "Research project".*Changes in Tax Change and Payment System: Jehovah's Witnesses in Ghana*" Explain that mutual funds are affected by long- and short-term taxes, but this is often cited for several years(Kwesi, Kwasi & Kojo, 2018).

Unemployment

Working people want to find a job, but they don't want to achieve it. According to the ED, unemployment often occurs when interest rates fall and costs increase, which hinders its use and use. But as Payman J points out, Isakintak says workers work two days a week before the community gets a job. in terms of research and research."*Taxes for the unemployed in Nigeria*" He confirmed that tax revenues are negative, but not a major consequence for unemployment in Nigeria.(Enueshike, 2021). "Research project". *Tax consequences of an unemployed company* "The completion of the tax credit has a negative impact on unemployment. (Chapters Zirgulis and Sar, 2017). This is an investigation." *Corporate tax and its impact on unemployment: a recent study in 15 countries*" Ensure that tax revenues affect unemployment in low-income areas (Rashid, 2023).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Material

These data from the World Bank website and UN data. The data collected is the end of tax revenue, foreign consumption, changes and unemployment costs in Indonesia, Malaysia, Cambodia, Vietnam and Myanmar from 2012 to 2022. There are five analyses, three of which differ from, for example, direct use of member countries (X1), savings (X2), income (X3) and domestic taxes (Y), as well as unemployment costs (Z).

Methods

The study also studied methods used to measure the impact of taxes on unemployment. The information discussed in the section on the system is the practice of obtaining consent machines to ensure the dissemination of information that includes multiple processes and ecclesiastical processes.

The structure of the study is as follow:

Number 1. Research programmes

The results of the changes can be demonstrated compared with regression analysis. An example of regression is:

$$Y = a + b_1 \ln X_1 + b_2 \ln X_2 + b_3 \ln X_3 + e \quad \dots (1)$$

$$Z = a + b \ln Y \quad \dots (2)$$

Message:

T: Tax revenue

X1: Foreign Domestic Investment

X2: Import

X3: Exchange rate

A: Unemployment.

A and B stand

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Think of an impressive X for Y

1. Multicollinearity Test

A similar experiment is conducted to see a strong relationship between different variables, as shown in the following data:

Table 1. Result test of Multicollinearity

Changes	X1	X2	X3
X1	1,000000	0,005632	0,195339
X2	0,005632	1,000000	0,193734
X3	0,195339	0,193734	1,000000

Source: eViews Output (2024)

In the information above, you can see X_1, X_2 and $X_3 < 0.85$. This means that the differences between X_1, X_2 and X_3 in this study are not very different in color (naupupal, 2021: 141)

2. Heterocedasticity Test

Source: Output-eviews (2024)

Based on the differential test results above the second cave (blue), the data do not exceed the range (500 and -500), which means that the equation is the same. Therefore, there are no symptoms of mental impairment or separation of the disease test (Napatipoulou, 2021; 143).

B. Explore previous ideas for Y and Z changes

1. Multicolonierity Test

A similar experiment is conducted to see a strong relationship between different variables, as shown in the following data

Table 2. Result test

Changes	Z	Y
Z	1,000000	0,468321
Y	0,468231	1,000000

Source: eViews Output (2024)

2. Heterocedasticity Test

Source: Output-eviews (2024)

B. Hypothesis (X1, X2, X3, to Y)

(a) Test T

In this study, the T-test was used to ensure that the changes were carried out part-time. T-test results can be found in this information:

Table 3. T-test result

Changes	Summary	Std.error	Number T	Review topics
C	23,03722	3,227025	7,138839	0,0000
Foreign Invesment	0,371116	0,032664	11,36155	0,0000
Import	0,709595	0,110627	6,414325	0,0000
Exchange Rate	-0,117135	0,100342	-1,167350	0,2485

Source: Eviews 12 (2024)

The above plan shows that (1) the transition FDI(X1) of 0.371116 has a sig value is 0.0000 < 0.05, and this means that the FDI difference has a positive and significant impact on tax revenue, (2) the information (X2) 0.709595 sig value is 0.0000 < 0.05, and this means that an effective and substantial tax change is useful, and (3) change (X3) -0.117135 and Sig value is 0.2585 > 0.05 value, This means that a change in changes has a negative effect that is indefensible.

B) F-Analysis

The F-test will be used in this study to determine if individual changes affect changes related to the same period. The F-test results can be found in the following information:

Table 4. F Test(X 1.X 2.X3 to Y)

R-square	0,862795
R-Custom	0,854724
SEE regression	0,193398
F-number	106,9021
Search (Number F)	0,000000

Source: eViews Output (2024)

From the table above, it can be seen that the GIS currency is $0.000 < 0.05$, which means that at the same time, the direct exchange rate, currency, and exchange rate have a significant impact on the tax collector's fees.

c. Determination Test (R2)

Use it to find out how much can be done in everything that can be done to explain the changes. The value of the Hebrew phrase R-squared as follows:

Table 5. R2 Result

R-square	0,862795
Adjust R-Square	0,854724
SEE regression	0,193398
F-number	106,9021
Search (Number F)	0,000000

Source: eViews Output (2024)

From the table above, you can be sure that the value of the adjusted R-square is about 0.854724 or 85.47%. It can be proven that 85.47% of cash, cash and exchange rates can be downloaded simultaneously to ensure that the decision is made to use reasonable cash, cash and exchange rates to describe the best business that is tax efficient. And there were 14.53% (100% - 85.47%) who came from other changes that were not studied in this way.

2. Hypothesis Y to Z

(a) Test T

In this study, the T-test was used to ensure that the changes were carried out part-time. T-test results can be found in this information:

Table 6. T-test result

Changes	Summary	Std.error	Number T	Review topics
C	-1,039758	0,499740	-2,080597	0,0423
Tax revenue	0,066546	0,017250	3,857796	0,0003

Source: Eviews 12 (2024)

The ordinary tax rate has interest rates of 0.066546 and 0.0003, which means that the tax has a tax effect of 0.06546 in terms of unemployment.

B. F-Analysis

The F-test will be used in this study to determine if individual changes affect changes related to the same period. The F-test results can be found in the following information:

Table 7. F Test Result (Y to Z)

R-square	0,219240
R-Custom	0,204509
SEE regression	0,466786
F-number	14,88259
Prob (Statistic F)	0,000312

Source: eViews Output (2024)

F Statistic is 0.000312 < 0.05, meaning tax changes have a significant impact on unemployment.

c. Determination Test (R2)

Use it to find out how much can be done in everything that can be done to explain the changes. The value of the Hebrew phrase R-squared as follows:

Table 8. R2 Square Result

R-square	0,219240
Adjust R-square	0,204509
SEE regression	0,466786
F-number	14,88259
Prob (Statistic F)	0,000312

Source: eViews Output (2024)

From the table above, the value of R-squared can be confirmed as 0.219240 or 21.92%. It can be noted that at the same time 21.92% of employees affect the tax, so the tax does not sound good to explain that the unemployment rate is bad. There were 78.08% (100% - 21.92%) arising from other changes that were not studied in this way.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Effects of direct taxes

The results of studies of foreign direct investment in Indonesia, Malaysia, Cambodia, Vietnam and Myanmar showed a balance sheet value of 0.37116 and a signification of 0.000 < 0.05, suggesting that foreign direct investment has a positive and significant impact on tax revenues. *Use of different countries* a field that is used abroad or can travel nationwide for the benefit of the capital; (Jingan, 2018). This coincides with a study called "Inspiration" *Use of different countries* in larger countries in the form of tax revenues" shows the positive benefits of spending tax revenues correctly (God's sign) *and al.*, 2019). and according to the study of "encouragement " *Use of different countries* and the distribution of tax revenue in cities that support the ASEAN system to ensure that foreign currency has a positive impact on tax revenues. (A, A, etc., 2023).

Import

This shows the effect of the tax change affecting the interest rate of 0.709595 and costing 0.000 < 0.05.

The process of purchasing a product or service from one place to another (Jordan, 2018, page 2) . This is consistent with a study called "Work Record Book Counting and Entry Outcomes," which cuts the interchange interval with the entry book, which at the same time has a significant impact.(Your quest, Revin & Edison, 2023). A study titled "Results of tax deposits: İma in Indonesia" suggests that currency growth will affect tax returns. (from Takahashi, 2012). Therefore, the government must set reasonable and untreated standards so that business owners can take on key responsibilities and reduce lies in the areas in which they work.

Effects of tax changes

The results of the survey show that changes in the country have negative consequences and cannot be used in tax revenues. This was evident from the results of the yield review from -0, 117135 cost 0.2485 > 0.05. It's about learning." *The change in the tax system in Kenya is commensurate with the cost of the change, which affects tax revenues in Kenya.*(Ruto, 2020). Other research." *The impact of tax changes Sub-Saharan in Africa and can fix the exchange rate directly at the tax rate in sub-Saharan Africa;* (Isaac,

Kamara & Peter, 2021). "Research project". *Changes in Tax Change and Payment System: Jehovah's Witnesses in Ghana* Explain that mutual funds are affected by long- and short-term taxes, but this is often cited for several years (Kwesi, Kwasi & Kojo, 2018). It is the state's responsibility to change taxes.

Tax consequences for the unemployed

The study confirmed that the unemployment rate was 0.066546 $0.0003 < 0.05$. This means that tax consequences are favourable and important for unemployment. When taxes rise, low taxes increase government spending and reduce unemployment. This is consistent with the research. "*Taxes for the unemployed in Nigeria*" He confirmed that tax revenues are negative, but not a major consequence for unemployment in Nigeria. (Enueshike, 2021). "Research project". *Tax consequences of an unemployed company* "The completion of the tax credit has a negative impact on unemployment. (Chapters Zirgulis and Sar, 2017). This is an investigation." *Corporate tax and its impact on unemployment: a recent study in 15 countries* Ensure that tax revenues affect unemployment in low-income areas (Rashid, 2023).

CONCLUSION

The results of the experiment showed that tax revenues are very useful at the same time, as shown by the Adjust-R2 value of 0.854724 or 85.47%. However, changes in foreign currency and income can to some extent affect tax efficiency and value, and changes in income can have a negative effect that cannot be applied to tax revenues. The impact of tax on unemployment is 0.066546 returns and $0.0003 < 0.05$ Check. This means that this reflects the positive and significant benefits of unemployed tax revenue, and the R-square costs 0.219240 or 21.92%.

REFERENCES

1. Ari, T.W., and Takahashi, S. (2012) "Tax-saving benefits: nature Indonesia has completed economic development.
2. Enueshike, P. (2021) "The impact of tax revenues on unemployment in Nigeria", *Journal of European Administration and Business Administration*.
3. Gilath, T. (2023) *Microeconomics*. Education: Canisius.
4. Jordan, M. (2018) *In Business and Abroad – Part II*. Jakarta: In Bushindo.
5. Indra, A. (2016) "Our local tax revenue was The poverty level has come at a high price", *JRAK*, 7(1), p. 10). Luke 1-10.
6. Inriana, M. and Setyowati, M. (2020) "The impact of economic development, direct ASEAN State Income Tax Income", *Journal of State Treasury and Public Policy*, 5(4). doi: doi.org/https://doi.org/10.33105/itrev.v5i4.240.
7. Isaac, K. O., Kamara, K. O. and Peter, I. M. (2021) in *Tax Changes Money in Sub-Sharana Africa*", *MPRA Letter*, No. 107762. available: https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/107762/1/MPRA_paper_107762.pdf%0A%0A.
8. Jhingan, M. (2018) *Economic planning and employment development*. Time for Countindo.
9. Kwes, I.O., Kvas, K. O. and Kojo, M. A. (2018) *Economics: Witness in Ghana, General and Applied Economics*. Research. *Money and Money*, 6. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/23322039.2018.1537822>%0A%0A.
10. Ngoc's son, N. (2023) "The impact of corporate unemployment tax: An example of VAR Methods", *Problems and Leadership Behavior*, 21(2), <http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21> pp. 111-123.
11. The Sun, A, p... (2023) "Implications of the use of alien and urban spaces. On the Reduction of Tax Revenues and Evils in ASEAN Countries", *Journal of Law, Administration and Science*, 3(2). doi: yes, <https://doi.org/10.54957/jolas.v3i2.477>.
12. Rasheed, M. (2023) "Corporate Tax and its impact on employment: recent education 15 OcED Board", *Marsland Press*. doi:DOI:10.7537/marsrsj130321.05.
13. Ruto, R. (2020) "Changing the amount of tax revenue in Kenya", *International Journal of Financial, Economic and Management Research*. Article 4, paragraph 12. Also available: https://ijebmr.com/uploads/pdf/archivepdf/2020/IJEBMR_650-2.pdf.
14. Soetrisno, N., Idiyani, R. and Edison, P. S. (2023) "The impact of changing the number of deposits in violation of the right of entry," *Journal of Business Administration*, 9(2).
15. SWidya, A. and al. (2019) "The benefits of using direct income Taxes on Berkem Land, Economy and Business, University of Indonesia.
16. Zirgulis, A. and Sartakas, T. (2017) "The impact of corporate taxation inactivity", *Financial Journal and Business Management*, 18(3), pp. 111-123.

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